
Evaluating Large Language Models for RDF Knowledge Graph Related Tasks - The LLM-KG-Bench-Framework 3

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Abstract

Current Large Language Models (LLMs) can work with structured information and even assist developing program code, but can they support working with Knowledge Graphs (KGs) as well? Which LLM is offering the best capabilities in the field of Semantic Web and Knowledge Graph Engineering (KGE)? Is it possible to determine this without checking many answers manually? The LLM-KG-Bench framework is designed to answer these questions. It consists of an extensible set of tasks for which the LLM answers are automatically evaluated, and covers different aspects of working with semantic technologies.

This article gives a description of the LLM-KG-Bench framework, its main concepts and the tasks implemented. In a benchmark run, a comprehensive dataset has been generated with it, evaluating more than 40 contemporary open and proprietary LLMs. Finally, this dataset is used for an analysis of the SPARQL related capabilities of the LLMs tested.

Keywords

LLM, RDF, SPARQL, Knowledge Graph, Benchmark, LLM-Evaluation

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The combination of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Knowledge Graphs (KGs) offers great synergetic potential for various knowledge-driven applications and is still gaining more traction within the research community. However, the ongoing rapid development in the field of Large Language Models (LLMs), makes it difficult to keep up with the latest developments and put them into context of prior work. Several initiatives for automated benchmarking, like BigBench¹, HELM², or Chatbot-Arena³, address the need for systematic evaluation of LLM performance. However, the tasks in scope of these evaluations are very general and do not address topics specifically related to KGs.

With the benchmarking framework *LLM-KG-Bench*, we are particularly focusing on automatically assessing and comparing LLMs regarding their capabilities to cope with Semantic Web technologies. The framework supports open weight and top-ranking commercial LLMs and includes a set of highly relevant tasks specific to Knowledge Graph Engineering (KGE), for instance, related to SPARQL queries and RDF KG serialization.

1.2 Research Questions

Our investigation has been guided by the following overarching research questions:

RQ 1. *Can KGE-related capabilities of LLMs be evaluated in an automated way?*

RQ 2. *Should specific LLMs be favored for specific tasks or KG data formats? And if so, to which extent do their capabilities differ and how can it be measured which LLM fits best for which task?*

And specific to SPARQL SELECT queries:

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RQ 3. *Can LLMs follow the syntactic rules of SPARQL SELECT queries?*

RQ 4. *Can LLMs parse the semantics of SPARQL SELECT queries and act accordingly?*

RQ 5. *Can LLMs write semantically correct SPARQL SELECT queries for a given question and KG?*

Contribution and Outline

We present here an overview on the current state of the LLM-KG-Bench framework together with an evaluation dataset on more than 40 current LLMs and an evaluation of the SPARQL SELECT related capabilities. The LLM-KG-Bench framework is developed for automated benchmarking of Knowledge Graph related capabilities of LLMs.

The main contribution of this article is threefold:

- We provide a description of the current state of the framework, including main concepts, API, supported model connectors and tasks
- We present a dataset on the evaluation of more than 40 LLMs. The dataset includes detailed logs, interaction data and the evaluation result. This enables other researchers to extend this dataset, reproduce our analysis or run additional analyses e.g. by updating the framework code and using the framework's reevaluation feature.
- As a demonstration of the frameworks' analytical capabilities and the generated dataset, we evaluate the *SPARQL SELECT* query related capabilities of the selected LLMs.

This is an extended version of previous work by Meyer et al. 2025⁴ with a similar use case as the one presented in Meyer et al. 2024⁵. The added contribution of this paper compared to our previous work consists of:

- providing a unified source of truth for the current state of the LLM-KG-Bench framework, especially based on current conference and workshop articles⁴⁻⁶
- a refined description of capabilities that an LLM needs to have in order to solve the benchmark tasks
- the enrichment of the previous result dataset by executing the benchmark framework against several top-ranked LLMs

- grouping and refining of the capability plots together with the computation of an aggregated score for the SPARQL related capabilities of the LLMs tested
- an improvement of the analysis of TTL versus JSON by including a per-model as well as a per-task summary.

2 Related Work

2.1 LLM Evaluation

Attempts on exploring and navigating the vast amount of LLMs are made in form of several LLM leaderboards, which provide evaluation services for LLMs in form of selections of benchmarks or workloads. Focusing mainly on commercial models, the *Chatbot Arena*^{1,3} lists scores for *MMLU*² and *MT-bench*⁷, and also calculates its own arena-score (based on prompts given users, processed by two models side-by-side and evaluated by the same user voting for his preferred answer). For open models, the *Open-LLM-Leaderboard*³ provides a list of benchmark results with over 2,000 tested models, and with scores for IfEval, BBH, MATH, GPQU, MUSR, MMLU, plus a carbon dioxide emission estimate. The most exhaustive list is provided by *HELM*^{4,2} which includes also domain-specific tests like LegalBench and MedQA. While a comparison of the individual benchmark suites is out of scope of this paper, none addresses Knowledge Graph Engineering (KGE) tasks.

Moreover, what is generally amiss is a benchmark execution framework that helps to deal with the particularities of RDF and KG-related workloads (format parsing, syntax check feed back loops, execution and evaluation of queries towards KGs, etc.). Although early attempts have been made by *Big Bench*¹, it is falling short of building an efficient base for evaluating LLM capabilities in the context of KGE tasks, due to insufficiencies of the provided Task API, along with the focus on multiple choice tasks and scores based on string or document similarities.

In the face of these issues, our LLM-KG-Bench framework aims to reduce complexity and facilitate creating, executing, evaluating, and analyzing KG-related tasks. Its procedures focus on the syntactically and semantically correct generation of RDF (i.e. in Turtle) and SPARQL.

Current efforts in benchmarking coding capabilities seem more closely related to characteristics of KGE capabilities benchmarking, at a conceptual level (e.g., with respect to output format requirements,

Table 1. Comparison of some of the LLM evaluation approaches mentioned here. Best values are marked with bold font. Only the LLM-KG-Bench framework automatically evaluates several Knowledge Graph Engineering (KGE) tasks and covers many LLMs in a benchmark run.

	LLMs covered	KGE topics	eval. type
BIG Bench ¹	many	no	automatic
HELM ²	many	no	automatic
Chatbot Arena ³	many	no	crowd
ChatGPT KG Experiments ¹⁶	GPT3.5, GPT4	several	manual
Text2KgBench ⁹	Vicuna, Alpaca-LoRA	Text2KG	automatic
AutoKG ¹⁰	4	Text2KG, Reasoning	manual
SparqlGen ¹²	GPT3	Text2Sparql	manual
LLM-KG-Bench 3	many	several	automatic

instruction complexity, and response evaluation strategies). Several leaderboards, like *Big Code Models Leaderboard*⁵ for Java, Javascript, and CPP, or *EvalPlus Leaderboard*⁶ for Python, assess the coding proficiency of LLMs using HumanEval, MultiPL-E, MBPP, respectively. We included some of the models ranked there into our test set.

2.2 RDF related evaluation

In the current literature⁷ that explores the combination of LLMs and KGs⁸, several attempts on evaluating the application of LLMs for KG related tasks are made. However, these LLM evaluations often focus on details for a very selective problem in a specific task area, like Text to RDF (e.g.,^{9,10}), Knowledge Graph Question Answering (KGQA, e.g.,¹¹), Text to SPARQL (e.g.,^{12,13}) or RML generation (e.g.,¹⁴). Unfortunately, many of these evaluations have been conducted manually, which causes scalability issues with respect to more repetitions and including more or newer models. In case an automated evaluation has been performed, the underlying code usually lacks adaptability to encompass new models or task variations. A benchmarking effort that is related to our interest in studying the JSON-LD capabilities, is *StructuredRAG*¹⁵. It consists of six tasks designed to assess LLM capabilities in following response format instructions according to JSON templates. Table 1 compares several of the mentioned LLM evaluation approaches with respect to the covered LLMs, addressed KGE tasks and their evaluation mode. Only the LLM-KG-Bench framework combines automatic evaluation for many covered LLMs and several KGE topics.

2.3 Text2Sparql and KBQA

The interpretation and generation of the query language SPARQL, being a core technology for accessing KG, is one especially relevant example of integrating Semantic Technology with LLMs.

Rangel et al.¹⁷ introduce a method for fine-tuning OpenLLaMA to generate SPARQL queries for question answering on life science knowledge graphs. Their approach leverages data augmentation techniques, such as the use of meaningful variable names and inline comments, which lead to improved accuracy in SPARQL query generation.

Bustamante and Takeda¹⁸ focus on enhancing the generation of SPARQL queries from natural language questions. They employ a GPT model to identify the most challenging aspects of the Text2SPARQL task, aiming to apply targeted solutions to these difficulties.

Avila et al.¹⁹ evaluate ChatGPT's performance in answering natural language questions on knowledge graphs. Their method, Auto-KGQAGPT, explores translating such questions into SPARQL queries using prompts that include relevant knowledge graph fragments.

Li et al.²⁰ address the performance drop seen in real-world conditions where high-quality annotated data is lacking. They propose the FlexKBQA framework, which uses template SPARQL queries that are converted into natural language questions via large language models (LLMs) to produce synthetic training data. This data is used to fine-tune a lightweight SPARQL generator, further refined with real queries to bridge the gap between synthetic and real-world inputs.

Diallo et al.²¹ provide a thorough evaluation comparing pre-trained language models (PLMs), non-pre-trained language models (NPLMs), and LLMs, along with various fine-tuning strategies. Their error analysis reveals that incorrect URIs, often caused by hallucinations, are a major source of failure in generated SPARQL queries. Hirigoyen et al.²² demonstrate that incorporating a copy mechanism can help mitigate such hallucinations.

Kovriguina et al.¹² present SPARQLGEN, a one-shot generation technique that uses LLMs to produce SPARQL queries. Their method includes the full context comprising the question, a relevant RDF subgraph, and an example query within a single prompt.

Pliukhin et al.²³ propose a similar approach to SPARQLGEN for query generation over the ORKG scholarly knowledge graph, enhanced with a

more advanced subgraph extraction method. Zahera et al.¹³ extend this by incorporating chain-of-thought prompting and using the GERBIL QA system¹¹.

Lehmann et al.²⁴ advocate the use of Controlled Natural Language (CNL) as a user interface due to its proximity to natural language. They show that CNL can be reliably and unambiguously translated into formal query languages like SPARQL, significantly reducing the need for large training datasets.

Diefenbach et al.²⁵ introduce two datasets for training and benchmarking QA systems on Wikidata: One derived from the SimpleQuestions dataset²⁶, and another based on user logs and feedback.

Dubey et al.²⁷ extend the LC-QuAD dataset with LC-QuAD 2.0²⁸, which is compatible with both Wikidata and DBpedia. The dataset comprises 30,000 questions, including paraphrases and corresponding SPARQL queries.

Banerjee et al.²⁹ explore various ways to integrate LLMs into standard knowledge graph workflows. Their focus is on models that can be fine-tuned with consumer-grade hardware, in contrast to approaches focusing on large-scale models used without additional training.

Frey et al.³⁰ demonstrate the long-term value of automated benchmarking through the LLM-KG-Bench platform. They compare multiple LLM iterations with a focus on their ability to handle RDF Turtle syntax, preserving responses for future evaluation. Heim et al.⁶ is an example of such a separate evaluation.

Hofer et al.¹⁴, consistent with the findings by Frey et al.^{30,31}, investigate LLM-driven RML mapping generation in Turtle. They find that while syntactic errors occur, most LLMs can correct these mistakes. Given that SPARQL is built on Turtle, the authors conduct their experiments as multi-turn dialogues with feedback loops for error correction.

3 The LLM-KG-Bench framework

Benchmarking LLMs involves significant time, financial costs, organizational effort, and the evaluation process can often be imprecise. LLM-KG-Bench is designed to simplify the creation of KG-related assessments while providing a foundational infrastructure for further development. Its main features are:

- **Modular and Extensible Framework:** Supports automated evaluation tasks using a comprehensive set of KG-extraction and evaluation-related helper methods.
- **Built-in Correction Cycles:** Implements dialogue-based correction cycles, enabling LLMs to revise previous mistakes.
- **Data Security:** Supports encryption of task data to prevent test data leakage into LLM training datasets.
- **Task Management:** Manages task configurations, evaluation orchestration, logging, and result persistence.
- **Result Analysis and Visualization:** Provides built-in tools for analyzing and visualizing evaluation results.
- **Broad Model Support:** Includes connectors for many contemporary LLMs.
- **Open-Source Codebase:** The framework is published as open source and welcomes extensions and community contributions.

In the following sections, we describe the basic concepts and infrastructure of LLM-KG-Bench framework in greater detail.

3.1 Architecture and Main Concepts

The main architecture is described in fig. 1, adapted version from Meyer et al.³². The LLM-KG-Bench framework is build around some main concepts we want to describe here, similar to⁴.

Evaluation Tasks: The *evaluation tasks* are the main building block of a *benchmark* and automatically evaluate the LLM answers. For the *prompt-answer-evaluate loop* the tasks provide the prompt and evaluation functionality.

Task Classes, Parametrized Tasks and Task Case Entries: Tasks are organized in *task classes*. Some task classes can be parametrized with task class-specific *task parameters* resulting in *parametrized task classes*.

Prompt-Answer-Evaluate Loop: The evaluation of LLMs is based on dialogues, consisting of prompts and answers. The prompt-answer-evaluate loop starts with the generation of an initial prompt that is sent to an LLM. In the next step, the produced answer is evaluated. Based on the evaluation result, the framework can decide to start a new prompt-answer-evaluate round or stop the dialogue. The idea is to make use of the chat capability of modern LLMs and their bigger supported context size

Figure 1. The main architecture of the LLM-KG-Bench framework. Source: GitHub page, updated version of Meyer et al. ³².

in order to get the answer closer to the correct one. The structure of these loops is shown in fig. 2a and an example dialogue is given in fig. 4.

LLM Connectors: The *LLM connectors* offer a consistent abstraction layer to interact with various supported LLMs. Several *LLM connector classes* are implemented in the LLM-KG-Bench framework as described in section 3.3. They can get parametrized to abstract specific LLMs.

Task Evaluation Iterations: We name one task evaluation loop consisting of one or more prompt-answer-evaluate rounds a *task evaluation iteration*, see also fig. 2b.

Task Executions: Since LLM answers are generated probabilistically, a configurable number of task iterations is executed, collectively forming a *task evaluation execution* for a specific task and a particular LLM, see also fig. 2b.

Benchmark Executions: A *benchmark execution* consists of all task executions for all combinations of tasks and models defined in the configuration, see also fig. 2b.

(a) The Prompt-Answer-Evaluate loop for the task — LLM interaction as organized by the framework. Prompting and evaluation is covered by the task, the answer is generated by the LLM.

(b) Different execution scopes: task iterations (includes one to many cycles of the prompt-answer-evaluate loop), task execution (includes all iterations), benchmark execution (includes all task executions for all combinations of tasks and LLMs defined for all iterations).

Figure 2. Overview of the evaluation workflow and execution scopes.

List Tasks and Task Case Entries: List tasks have a list of *task case entries*, where each entry defines a distinct exercise resulting in a specific prompt and expected answer. For each *task iteration* one *task case entry* is selected from this list. All *task case entries* are evaluated by the same *list task*.

Benchmark Configuration: A *benchmark configuration* specifies the tasks and models to be included in a benchmark run together with the number of iterations per task execution.

Execution Configuration A *benchmark configuration* can be executed as a whole or with a selection of tasks and models defined by command line parameters.

Result Reevaluation With result reevaluation existing task model interaction data can be feed into the tasks' evaluation code. This could help for example to get updated results with updated evaluation code without new LLM interactions.

3.2 Tasks API

Tasks are implemented following the Task API as a common interface between tasks, framework and model connectors. In LLM-KG-Bench framework Version 3, a major update of the Task API was introduced

Figure 3. UML class diagram of the Task API and its reference by some example tasks. All task classes implement the *AbstractLlmKgBenchInterface* via an inheritance connection. A task can be described with a *TaskInfo* object. A *TaskExecutionInfo* references this *TaskInfo* object for the documentation.

together with new helper classes. Figure 3 shows the UML class diagram of the new Task API.

Benchmark tasks in LLM-KG-Bench do implement the interface *AbstractLlmKgBenchTaskInterface* which enables a rough compatibility with the BigBench task classes. As supplement, it defines methods for the Evaluate and Prompt steps of the Prompt-Answer-Evaluate loop as well as methods for the serialization and deserialization of tasks.

Here, the following methods are especially important:

getNextPrompt: combines an evaluation and prompting step. If no new prompt is generated the prompt-answer-evaluate loop ends.

finalizeEvaluation: is called at the end of the prompt-answer-evaluate loop and creates a final evaluation result for this task evaluation iteration.

condenseTaskData: creates a serializable representation of this concrete task case entry. This offers the possibility for later continuation or reevaluation.

createTaskFromCondensedData: initializes a task from the representation given by *condenseTaskData*

The abstract implementation *AbstractLlmKgBenchTaskClass* helps to reduce redundant code and eases the concrete task implementation. For the two main variations of tasks, single-prompt tasks and dialogue-tasks, specialized abstract classes are provided. Tasks that store their task data in an encrypted file can benefit from the abstract class *AbstractFileListTaskImplementation*.

This new task API offers more granularity for the interaction of the LLM-KG-Bench framework with the tasks compared to the interface used in prior versions of the LLM-KG-Bench framework and BigBench. The central framework logic orchestrates the prompt-answer-evaluate loop(fig. 2a). The new task API gives the central framework logic more flexibility in the orchestration, reduces error possibilities and reduces repeated code in tasks.

3.3 Model Connectors and Supported Models

Model connectors are responsible for offering standardized APIs to LLMs. They are defined similar to the BIG bench model class. The main method offered is `generate_text(inputs, ...)->str`, taking a single prompt or dialogue and returning the LLMs answer.

The LLM-KG-Bench framework offers several model connectors:

OpenAI / ChatGPT: Connector for OpenAI-compatible LLMs like GPT-3.5, GPT-4, GPT-4t, GPT-4o and GPT-o1 via the OpenAI python library⁸ and REST API⁹. Many other LLM providers offer a compatible REST endpoint. They can be integrated with this connector as well.

Google / Gemini: Connector for LLMs from Google like Gemini 1.5 or Gemini 2.0 via the Google python library¹⁰ and REST API¹¹.

Anthropic / Claude: Connector for LLMs from Anthropic from Claude 1.0 to Claude 3.5. The connector uses the Anthropic REST API¹² using the offered Python library¹³.

vLLM : Runtime for self-hosted LLMs^{14,33}. This library is compatible to many open LLMs and enables serving and inferencing them.

3.4 Benchmark Tasks

Several tasks are implemented in the LLM-KG-Bench framework as described in several articles^{4,5,30-32}. This includes especially the following task classes:

RDF-related Tasks:

FactExtractStatic: The LLM is instructed to extract facts from a given textual fact sheet and create a corresponding Turtle KG. See also^{31,32}.

RdfConnectionExplainStatic: This task asks the LLM to find the shortest connection between two nodes in a small RDF graph. The shortest path shall be output as a list of IRIs. Four variations present the graph in different serialization formats: JSON-LD, N-Triples, Turtle and RDF/XML. See also^{4,31}.

RdfFriendCount: For a simple RDF graph with, respectively, only one node and one edge type, the LLM is asked to identify the node with the most incoming edges. Again, there are four variations covering the different serialization formats JSON-LD, N-Triples, Turtle and RDF/XML. See also^{4,31}.

RdfSyntaxFixList: The LLM is instructed to correct a syntactically invalid RDF graph. The variations cover the serialization formats JSON-LD, N-Triples and Turtle. For more details, see⁴.

TurtleSampleGeneration: In this task, the LLM shall generate small Turtle knowledge graphs satisfying given requirements. See also^{31,32}.

SPARQL-related Tasks:

Sparql2AnswerList: Given a small KG and a SPARQL SELECT query, the LLM shall return the respective result set for the query. Here, the KG is given in the JSON-LD or Turtle format. See also⁵.

Text2AnswerList: In this task, the LLM is instructed to return the result set answering a given textual question on a given KG. This is a variation of the Sparql2Answer task with the same logic but without a *SPARQL SELECT* query. Again, the variations introduce the KG in either the JSON-LD or Turtle format. For more details, see⁵.

Figure 4. Fictive example dialogue for the RdfSyntaxFixList task with a missing dot in Turtle syntax. Some text left out is marked with "...". The LLM's first answer is missing the expected code block with the fixed Turtle which is corrected in the second answer. Source ⁴

Text2SparqlList: Given a KG and its description, the LLM shall construct a SPARQL SELECT query corresponding to a given natural language query. The KG is either given completely or partly as a subgraph. Alternatively, one variation provides the KG schema instead of the graph itself. Moreover, the variations cover seven different KG datasets. See also table 3 and ⁵.

SparqlSyntaxFixingList: Similar to the RdfSyntaxFixList task, the LLM gets a SPARQL SELECT query with syntax errors shall return a corrected query. See also ⁵.

The prompts are designed in a way that keeps ambiguity as low as possible. All requirements that we expect the LLM to respect are stated explicitly, e.g., stick with the original formatting, or answer with just one markdown fenced code block ... no other text. At the same time, we avoid LLM-specific prompt optimization for a fair comparison across different models. An example dialog is shown in fig. 4.

Table 2. Mapping of the task types to the different task aspects and research questions covered. Adopted from⁵

research question: task aspect:	RQ 3 syntax read	RQ 3 syntax create	RQ 4 semantic read	RQ 5 semantic create
SPARQL Syntax Fixing (SSF)	x	x	-	-
SPARQL to Answer (S2A)	x	-	x	-
Text to SPARQL (T2S)	-	x	-	x
Text to Answer (T2A)	-	-	-	-

3.5 Benchmark Datasets and KGs Used for Task Implementations

There are several benchmark datasets available which contain pairs of *SPARQL SELECT* queries and textual natural language questions for specific knowledge graphs. We selected and implemented benchmark tasks for a couple of current datasets for smaller and bigger knowledge graphs. Only English textual questions were used as we focus on *SPARQL* here and not language capabilities. A total of five tuples, each consisting of a question and corresponding *SPARQL* query, was manually selected from each dataset. This allows to rerun the tasks more often to reduce the random noise in the results.

Organizational dataset and KG The smallest KG used is an organizational KG¹⁶. We use it here together with a corresponding dataset¹⁵ of question and *SPARQL* pairs created by Brei et al.³⁴.

Organizational Numeric We created an additional variant of the organizational dataset and KG with numerical IRIs (first 3 digits of hash) and same questions.

CoyPu-Mini dataset and KG Brei et al.³⁴ published as well another dataset based on a small subset of the CoyPu KG¹⁶. This sub graph is small enough to fit into context size of LLMs evaluated here. We added lists of relevant IRIs and schema information.

Beastuary dataset and KG The Beastuary dataset and KG¹⁷ was presented by Kovriguina et al.¹². It offers for each question a relevant sub graph and a list of IRIs. We derived relevant schema information from these IRI lists.

SPARQL SELECT Query Syntax Errors We took one question and *SPARQL* pair from LC-QuAD and derived 5 tests from it by inserting different kinds of syntax errors, one error per test.

Table 3. Overview on the different SPARQL related tasks implemented within LLM-KG-Bench framework

task type	dataset subset	task	KG Info type	KG info format
SSF	Syntax-Errors	SSF-LC-QuAD	not needed here	not needed here
S2A	Organizational	S2A-Orga	full KG	Turtle or JSON-LD
T2S	Organizational	T2S-Orga	full KG	Turtle
	Organizational-Numeric	T2S-OrgaNum	full KG + IRIs + Labels	Turtle + table
	Beastuary	T2S-Beast-Graph	KG subset	Turtle
		T2S-Beast-Schema	schema subset	Turtle
		T2S-Beast-Subschema	schema subset	Turtle
CoyPu-Mini	T2S-Beast-Iris	IRIs	list	
	T2S-CoyPu-Graph	full KG	Turtle or JSON-LD	
	T2S-Coypu-Schema	schema subset	Turtle or JSON-LD	
T2A	Organizational	T2S-Coypu-Iris	IRIs	list
		T2A-Orga	full KG	Turtle or JSON-LD

The list of SPARQL related benchmark tasks created based on these resources in the *LLM-KG-Bench* framework is given in table 3.

3.6 General Task Characterization

For a structured task characterization, we draw from frameworks from cognitive psychology and educational research. Bloom’s Taxonomy³⁵ was originally developed to classify educational objectives based on the level of cognitive complexity required. It is based on behavioral observations of learning processes and was later revised to better fit modern views of cognitive psychology³⁶. Part of that revision includes the separation between what is known from what is done with it, leading to a Knowledge Dimensions framework³⁶. It distinguishes between types of knowledge required for different tasks. Relational Complexity Theory³⁷ was originally developed in developmental and comparative psychology and draws the notion of relational arity from formal systems in logic and computer science, including relational database theory. It models task difficulty as a function of the number of simultaneous relations that must be processed. Together, these models provide a basis for analyzing the cognitive-inspired and structural demands that the benchmark tasks impose.

The values in the characterization are assigned based on the minimal cognitive and structural requirements expected for successful task completion. Cognitive processes such as *Understand* are assigned when tasks require interpreting given information, while *Apply* corresponds

Table 4. Task characterization according to Bloom’s Taxonomy³⁵, the Knowledge Dimensions framework³⁶ and Relational Complexity Theory³⁷.

Task	Cognitive Process	Knowledge Dimension	Relational Complexity
RDF related:			
FactExtractStatic	Understand, Create	Conceptual, Procedural	Medium
RdfConnectionExplainState	Understand, Analyze	Conceptual	Medium
RdfFriendCount	Apply	Procedural	Low
RdfSyntaxFixList	Understand, Apply	Factual, Procedural	Low
TurtleSampleGeneration	Understand, Create	Conceptual, Procedural	Medium
SPARQL related:			
Sparql2AnswerList	Understand, Apply	Conceptual, Procedural	Low
Text2AnswerList	Understand, Apply	Conceptual, Procedural	Low
Text2SparqlList	Understand, Create	Conceptual, Procedural	Low
SparqlSyntaxFixingList	Understand, Apply	Factual, Procedural	Low

to the execution of known procedures. *Create* is used when tasks involve generating new content and *Analyze* when tasks require decomposing and interpreting relations between elements. For knowledge dimensions, *Factual* knowledge is assigned when specific syntactic or terminological information is needed, *Conceptual* when structural or relational understanding is necessary and *Procedural* when correct application of methods is required. Relational complexity is rated as *Low* when tasks involve isolated or simple binary relations, and as *Medium* when multiple entities and relations must be coordinated simultaneously. Note that not all categories across the frameworks are represented, as the current set of tasks does not span the full theoretical space. The characterization is shown in table 4.

4 Experiment

We utilized the LLM-KG-Bench framework to evaluate a list of over 30 LLMs with a selection of tasks. The results containing the full dialog and evaluation data for all this LLM interaction is documented and publicly available for further analysis. Whenever new LLMs are of interest, their data can get added to the initial dataset⁴. With the reevaluation feature the evaluation on these dialogs can get computed again with maybe updated code without new interaction with the LLMs. An example for a statistical analysis on existing data generated is⁶.

In the following section we outline the experiment setup and some analysis results from this evaluation.

4.1 Experiment Setup

We adopted the default configuration to define the tasks and models included in this evaluation. As a trade-off between resource usage and confidence, we have decided to conduct 20 iterations for the proprietary LLMs and 50 iterations for the open LLMs.

4.1.1 Selected Tasks The benchmark was executed on the following tasks that are described in section 3.4 and in the code repository:

- RdfSyntaxFixList: For Turtle, JSON-LD and N-Triples as graph format
- RdfConnectionExplainStatic: For Turtle, JSON-LD, RDF/XML and N-Triples as graph format
- RdfFriendCount: For Turtle, JSON-LD, RDF/XML and N-Triples as graph format
- SparqlSyntaxFixingList
- Sparql2AnswerList: For Organizational graph
- Text2SparqlList: For Organizational graph, Coypu-Mini and Beastiary

4.1.2 Selection of Proprietary LLMs To get an overview on the current state-of-the-art proprietary models we selected three long-term high-ranked model families from the Chatbot Arena Leaderboard: OpenAI GPT, Google Gemini and Anthropic Claude. From these families, we selected the current models in various sizes and also included the latest GPT-3.5 for comparability with other results. The selected models together with their context size are shown in table 5

4.1.3 Selection of Open LLMs We based our selection of state-of-the-art open LLMs on the Open LLM Leaderboard³⁸ and used the average score over all included benchmarks as our reference value. The selection criteria were that the model is instruction-finetuned, as required by the task construction of the LLM-KG-bench framework, has less than 80B parameters because of a limited amount of available hardware resources and is a base model, i.e., not a fine-tuned version of another model. With the latter requirement, we wanted to stick to mature and popularly used LLMs that are not just optimized to achieve a slightly higher score on one or few benchmarks than a base model.

The models fulfilling all our criteria and were among the TOP-4 models based on the average benchmark scores, disregarding models of the same

family with lower scores, were Qwen2-72B-Instruct, Meta-Llama-3.1-70B-Instruct, solar-pro-preview-instruct and Phi-3.5-MoE-instruct. Here, we excluded solar-pro-preview-instruct from our selection since it only supports a context length of up to 4096k Tokens and not all prompts of tasks included in the run fitted within this limit. For the remaining three models, we also included all models of their larger model families that matched our requirements, i.e., we also tested all models of the Llama3³⁹, Qwen2^{40,41}, and Phi3⁴² families fulfilling our requirements. Additionally, we included a Qwen3 and Llama4 model as well as two DeepSeek models.

In addition, we wanted to test open LLMs that are fine-tuned or explicitly optimized on code since they could potentially better understand and produce structured data as required for the tasks included in the LLM-KG-Bench. Here, we consulted the EvalPlus Leaderboard⁴³ and used the reported models' Mostly Basic Python Programming (MBPP) Benchmark score as our reference value to assess the code-producing quality of the models. Again, we excluded models that were only finetuned versions of a code-finetuned or -optimized base model, had more than 80B parameters or were not instruction-finetuned. Moreover, we only searched for models that are fine-tuned or explicitly optimized on code. Finally, we included the Top-3 models satisfying the criteria in our runs, namely Qwen2.5-Coder-32B-Instruct⁴⁰, DeepSeek-Coder-33B-Instruct⁴⁴ and OpenCoder-8B-Instruct⁴⁵.

4.2 Experiment Results

With the configuration described we generated a dataset containing the detailed conversations and the evaluations for 20 to 50 iterations per task and model. In the following section we show some analysis on tasks, models and the preference on input KG format.

4.2.1 Task Result Examples For each task a box plot was generated, containing the individual values for the most important score for each model tested. Due to limited space, we show here a selection for three tasks in fig. 5. The rest is available in the dataset repository.

Our evaluation of SPARQL related capabilities is mainly organized around the task types SparqlSyntaxFixing(SSF), Sparql2Answer(S2A) and Text2Sparql(T2S). For SSF and T2S we selected the `max_combined` score, which is 0.2 for syntactically correct but wrong queries. Figures 5a and 5c show several LLMs seem to have no

Table 5. Details for the models selected for the experiment presented here and the iterations evaluated per model and task combination. The parameter count of proprietary models is not documented and marked with a question mark (?) here. Proprietary model families are OpenAI-GPT, Google-Gemini and Anthropic-Claude. Extended version of ⁴.

Family	Model	Parameter	Context	iterations
OpenAI-GPT	ChatGPT 3.5 turbo	?	16k	20
	ChatGPT 4o	?	128k	20
	ChatGPT 4o-mini	?	128k	20
	ChatGPT o1	?	128k	20
	ChatGPT o1-mini	?	128k	20
Google-Gemini	Gemini 2.0 Flash	?	128k-1M	20
	Gemini 1.5 Pro	?	128k-2M	20
	Gemini 1.5 Flash	?	128k-1M	20
Anthropic-Claude	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	?	200k	20
	Claude 3.5 Haiku	?	200k	20
Qwen ^{40,41}	Qwen2-0.5B-Instruct	0.5B	32k	50
	Qwen2-1.5B-Instruct	1.5B	32k	50
	Qwen2-7B-Instruct	7B	128k	50
	Qwen2-57B-A14B-Instruct	57B (active: 14B)	64k	50
	Qwen2-72B-Instruct	72B	128k	50
	Qwen2.5-0.5B-Instruct	0.5B	32k	50
	Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct	1.5B	32k	50
	Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	3B	32k	50
	Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	7B	128k	50
	Qwen2.5-14B-Instruct	14B	128k	50
	Qwen2.5-32B-Instruct	32B	128k	50
	Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct	72B	128k	50
	Qwen2.5-Coder-32B-Instruct	32B	128k	50
	Qwen3.0-235b-a22b	235B(active 22B)	41k	50
	Meta-Llama ³⁹	Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct	8B	8k
Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct		70B	8k	50
Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct		8B	128K	50
Llama-3.1-70B-Instruct		70B	128K	50
Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct		1B	128K	50
Llama-3.2-3B-Instruct		3B	128K	50
Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct		70B	128K	50
Llama-4.0-Maveric		400B (active: 17B)	1M	50
Microsoft-Phi ⁴²	Phi-3-mini-128k-instruct	3.8B	128k	50
	Phi-3-small-128k-instruct	7B	128k	50
	Phi-3-medium-128k-instruct	14B	128k	50
	Phi-3.5-mini-instruct	3.8B	128k	50
	Phi-3.5-MoE-instruct	42B (active: 6.6B)	128k	50
Infly-OpenCoder ⁴⁵	OpenCoder-8B-Instruct	8B	8k	50
Deepseek-ai ⁴⁴	deepseek-coder-33b-instruct	33B	16k	50
	deepseek-chat-v3-0324	685B (active: 37B)	64K-164K	50
	deepseek-r1	671B (active: 37B)	64K-164K	50

problem answering with a syntactically correct SPARQL query with scores ≥ 0.2 . As can be seen in fig. 5b several LLMs answered correct with the expected result set for the given SPARQL SELECT queries.

Figure 5. Selection of box plots for task score values of the LLMs evaluated. The mean value is indicated with a circle, individual score values for each iteration are indicated with crosses.

In fig. 5c a box plot for the difficult task T2S for the Organizational-Numerical dataset is shown. Several semantically wrong answers were encountered, but Claude 3.5 Haiku & Sonnet, GPT 4o and Gemini 1.5 Pro provide good answers in this special case.

4.2.2 Capability Plots To get a quick overview on LLM models the LLM-KG-Bench framework can create capability plots⁴. They aggregate result scores for each model into categories according to a configuration

file. For the analysis of SPARQL capabilities we decided to use the following categories:

Syn-1: Working with *SPARQL SELECT* queries with first answer. This includes the `0_answerParse` scores (first answer per iteration) from task types `SparqlSyntaxFixing(SSF)` and `Text2Sparql(T2S)`.

Syn-Max: Working with *SPARQL SELECT* queries with correction possibility in dialog. This includes the `max_answerParse` scores (best answer per iteration) from the same task types as Syn-1.

Sem-R: Working according to semantics of *SPARQL SELECT* queries. This includes the `combinedF1` score of the `Sparql2Answer(S2A)` task type.

Sem-W-1: Creating semantically correct *SPARQL SELECT* queries with first answer. This includes the `0_combined` scores (first answer per iteration) from `Text2Sparql(T2S)` task types.

Sem-W-Max: Creating semantically correct *SPARQL SELECT* queries with correction possibility in dialog. This includes the `max_combined` scores (best answer per iteration) from `Text2Sparql(T2S)` task types.

fig. 6 shows a selection of typical capability plots for LLMs. Plots for all LLMs evaluated can be found in the supplemental material.

About a quarter of the models have plots similar to fig. 6a showing an almost perfect result with only slight problems with the writing of semantically correct *SPARQL SELECT* queries. For these models the framework would benefit from the inclusion of more complex benchmark datasets.

The rest of the models had more problems with answering the tasks resulting in plots like figs. 6b and 6c. Moreover, some very small models from Llama and Qwen family had even worse plots.

Two models, DeepSeek-Coder and OpenCoder revealed strong problems with the `Sparql2Answer` Task type resulting in low values for the Semantic Read capabilities. This is especially interesting, as their results in the rest of the categories are very good.

Figure 6e shows Llama-3-8B benefits from the correction infos in the dialog. The first answer was often improved during the dialog. Other LLMs evaluated here seem to have fewer benefit from the dialog.

Figure 6. Selection of typical capability plots for the evaluated LLMs. The scores of the models are aggregated along the following capabilities: *Syn-1* = Syntax of first answer; *Syn-max* = Syntax of best answer per iteration; *Sem-R* = Semantic Read; *Sem-W-1* = Semantic Write of first answer; *Sem-W-max* = Semantic Write of best answer per iteration. The black line shows the mean value, the blue area the standard deviation. Scores range from 0 to best value 1.

Understanding the syntax of *SPARQL SELECT* queries seems to be much easier for LLMs than the other capabilities. Most models show syntax understanding capability scores that are higher than the rest of the capability scores. Especially small models have a capability plot similar to fig. 6f, showing a good syntax understanding but big problems with the other capabilities.

Aside from the capability compasses, we also aggregated all scores in table 6. Although the values behind these scores have a high variance, the scores can give a first impression of the SPARQL capabilities. It is

Table 6. Combined scores of the SPARQL related capabilities of the LLMs tested. The categories combined into the single score are described in section 4.2.2.

ModelName	Score	ModelName	Score	ModelName	Score
Claude 3.5 Haiku	0,94	GPT4o-mini 2024/07	0,87	OpenCoder-8B	0,55
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	0,94	Llama-3.0-70B	0,86	Phi-3.0-medium-128k	0,5
Qwen-2.5-Coder-32B	0,93	Llama-3.3-70B	0,85	Phi-3.5-mini	0,49
GPT4o 2024/11	0,91	Qwen-2.0-72B	0,85	Llama-3.1-8B	0,42
GPTo1-pre 2024/09	0,91	Gemini 2.0 Flash Exp	0,85	Llama-3.0-8B	0,41
Qwen-2.5-72B	0,91	Qwen-2.5-14B	0,81	Phi-3.0-mini-128k	0,39
Gemini 1.5 Pro	0,9	Qwen-2.5-32B	0,81	Phi-3.0-small-128k	0,39
Deepseek-R1	0,9	GPT3.5 2024/01	0,8	Qwen-2.5-1.5B	0,32
Gemini 1.5 Flash	0,9	Phi-3.5-MoE	0,74	Llama-3.2-3B	0,23
Qwen-3-235B	0,89	Qwen-2.5-7B	0,73	Qwen-2.0-1.5B	0,2
GPTo1-mini 2024/09	0,89	Deepseek-Coder-33B	0,73	Qwen-2.5-0.5B	0,11
Llama-3.1-70B	0,89	Qwen-2-57B-A14B	0,7	Llama-3.2-1B	0,03
Llama-4-Maverick	0,87	Qwen-2.0-7B	0,58	Qwen-2.0-0.5B	0,01
Deepseek-Chat-v3	0,87	Qwen-2.5-3B	0,57		

interesting to see that open weight models are competitive in relation to the proprietary models.

4.2.3 Model Preferences on Input Format After running each task both on TTL and JSON-LD serializations of the same knowledge graph, we wanted to find out whether there is a preference for a certain format (i.e., a higher score when using one format over the other). To that end, we conducted several t-tests; both on the task level and the model level. The latter helps us understand if any given model has an overall preference for a certain input format, while the former gives us a better understanding on a per-task basis.

Looking at table 7, we can see that seven models have an overall preference for TTL, while eight models performed overall better on JSON-LD serializations. In contrast to that, 25 models do not have any kind of preference, leaving us with the conclusion that there is no universally preferred format.

Looking at the table 7 as a whole, we can see that preferences for one format over the other appear roughly equally distributed. However, there are some clusters like the Llama family of models preferring JSON, or Qwen leaning more towards TTL.

This might have to do with the amount of training data that covers TTL versus that which covers JSON. Unfortunately, as not all training data is publicly available, we cannot investigate this further.

When looking at the global preferences per task, we find that the Text2Answer and Sparql2Answer tasks appear to be easier to solve when operating on a TTL formatted knowledge graph. In contrast to that,

Table 7. Result of two-sided t-tests checking for a preference for Turtle (TTL) vs. JSON-LD serialization. Preferences are expected if the confidence interval is at least 95%, bold font indicates 99% or better. Extended from Meyer et al. ⁴

	RdfConnectionAllTasks	ExplainStatic	RdfFriendCount-1	RdfFriendCount-2	Sparql2AnswerList	FixListOrga	Text2AnswerListOrga
Claude 3.5 Haiku	TTL	JSON	TTL	TTL	-	-	-
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Deepseek-Coder-33B	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-
GPT3.5 2024/01	-	-	JSON	JSON	-	-	TTL
GPT4o 2024/11	-	-	-	-	JSON	-	-
GPT4o-mini 2024/07	TTL	-	-	TTL	-	-	TTL
GPTo1-mini 2024/09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
GPTo1-pre 2024/09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gemini 1.5 Flash	TTL	-	TTL	-	-	-	-
Gemini 1.5 Pro	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gemini 2.0 Flash Exp	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Llama-3.3-70B	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-
Meta-Llama-3-70B	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-
Meta-Llama-3-8B	-	TTL	-	-	-	-	-
Meta-Llama-3.1-70B	-	-	-	-	JSON	TTL	-
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-
Meta-Llama-3.2-1B	JSON	-	-	-	JSON	-	-
Meta-Llama-3.2-3B	-	JSON	TTL	TTL	JSON	-	-
deepseek-chat-v3-0324	-	JSON	TTL	TTL	-	-	-
deepseek-r1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
llama-4-maverick	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	-	-	-
OpenCoder-8B	-	-	-	-	-	TTL	-
Phi-3-medium-128k	TTL	TTL	-	JSON	-	-	TTL
Phi-3-mini-128k	-	-	-	JSON	JSON	-	-
Phi-3-small-128k	-	JSON	-	-	TTL	-	-
Phi-3.5-MoE	JSON	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	TTL	-
Phi-3.5-mini	-	TTL	JSON	-	JSON	TTL	-
Qwen2-0.5B	-	-	-	JSON	-	-	-
Qwen2-1.5B	JSON	TTL	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-
Qwen2-57B-A14B	TTL	-	-	-	JSON	TTL	TTL
Qwen2-72B	-	-	-	-	JSON	-	-
Qwen2-7B	-	JSON	-	-	-	-	TTL
Qwen2.5-0.5B	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Qwen2.5-1.5B	-	-	-	-	JSON	-	-
Qwen2.5-14B	-	TTL	-	-	-	-	TTL
Qwen2.5-32B	TTL	-	TTL	TTL	JSON	JSON	-
Qwen2.5-3B	-	JSON	-	-	JSON	-	-
Qwen2.5-72B	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	-	-	TTL
Qwen2.5-7B	TTL	JSON	-	-	-	TTL	TTL
Qwen2.5-Coder-32B	TTL	-	TTL	TTL	-	-	-
Solar-pro-preview-22B	-	-	-	-	JSON	-	-
All Models	-	-	JSON	JSON	JSON	TTL	TTL

counting friends seems to work better for JSON KGs. This could come from the fact that in order to find the person with the most incoming connections, the model needs to be able to parse the knowledge graph and have some notion of what an array is and how to count. In contrast, extracting facts (or answers in that case) profits from having the desired

answers close to the question subjects to not overextend the context size of the LLM, which is a strength of TTL.

Looking at the table, it is important to note that a model having no preference could mean one of these two things:

1. The model performs equally well on both formats and has no problem solving the task, no matter what. This is the case for Gemini 1.5 Pro, GPTo1 and some others.
2. The model has big problems solving the task. This is, for instance, the case for Qwen2 0.5B.

The former is a desired state as this relieves the user of the burden of having to choose a serialisation that maximizes the quality of the results, while models having preferences in certain areas indicate that they are still growing towards that state. To find out whether a model falls into the former or the latter category, one should cross reference the table with the corresponding capability compass.

5 Discussion and Outlook

Coming back to the research questions, the LLM-KG-Bench framework helps answering them.

RQ1: We showed here and in previous works^{5,31} the possibilities for automated evaluation of KGE-related capabilities. The LLM-KG-Bench framework is open for further development to support additional KGE task areas.

RQ2: In the analysis of the experiment result and in previous work^{5,6,30,31} we could identify ways to distinguish the KGE related capabilities of different LLMs. For *SPARQL SELECT* queries we propose here the scores calculated in table 6 as guidance.

RQ3: At least for the tasks evaluating the understanding of *SPARQL SELECT* queries syntax seems to be possible most of the time for most evaluated LLMs as shown in fig. 5a and in Meyer et al.⁵. Further work is needed to check this claim for more complex queries and errors.

RQ4: Figure 5b shows at least some LLMs seem to have no problems with working according to the semantics of *SPARQL SELECT* queries.

RQ5: At least for the evaluated tasks, the creation of semantically correct *SPARQL SELECT* queries seems to be possible most of the time for some LLMs, when looking at fig. 5c and the good capability plot type in fig. 6a. However, this also needs to be checked for other more complex queries. Moreover, it is important to consider that the evaluation is currently only done based on the answer set which does not necessarily mean that the semantic of the *SPARQL SELECT* query is correct.

Still there are some things to keep in mind. The answer quality of LLMs can vary even on small changes in prompt or task. We tested only with a limited amount of tasks and task entries. The automated evaluation could miss important aspects of the answer. For example the *SPARQL SELECT* queries generated were tested only extensional on the result set generated which does not necessary mean the query was well formulated to match the expected semantics. Although we tried to hide the benchmark data, we can not guarantee no LLM is trained with them as we want to keep the benchmark and it's results open and reproducible.

Further work is needed to include more datasets into the framework, extend the list of tasks to cover more aspects related to Knowledge Graphs and extend the analytical capabilities of the framework. The framework and the evaluation data generated is publicly available to enable contribution. And as the number of LLMs published and the size of datasets generated with the framework grows, new ways to check the results are needed. Maybe we could utilize another level of LLMs to check on the automated evaluation results for details missed and highlight this findings for manual inspection. This way the evaluation could remain deterministic and reproducible but we gain another level of checks and maybe even insight.

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Supplemental material

The framework source code and generated result datasets are publicly available:

- LLM-KG-Bench Framework Code:
<https://github.com/AKSW/LLM-KG-Bench/tree/v3.0.1>
(DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15336433](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336433))
- Generated Dataset:
<https://github.com/AKSW/LLM-KG-Bench-v3-0-results/tree/extended>

Notes

1. Leaderboard Chatbot Arena: <https://huggingface.co/spaces/lmarena-ai/chatbot-arena-leaderboard>
2. Description MMLU on HELM: <https://crfm.stanford.edu/2024/05/01/helm-mmlu.html>
3. Leaderboard Open LLM: https://huggingface.co/spaces/open-llm-leaderboard/open_llm_leaderboard
4. Leaderboard HELM: <https://crfm.stanford.edu/helm/lite/latest/#/leaderboard>
5. Leaderboard Big Code Models: <https://huggingface.co/spaces/bigcode/bigcode-models-leaderboard>
6. Leaderboard EvalPlus: <https://evalplus.github.io/leaderboard.html>
7. Updated literature overview: <https://github.com/zjukg/KG-LLM-Papers>
8. Repository OpenAI python: <https://github.com/openai/openai-python>
9. Description OpenAI REST API: <https://platform.openai.com/docs/api-reference/chat>
10. Repository Google Connector for LLMs: <https://github.com/google-gemini/generative-ai-python>
11. Description Google API: <https://ai.google.dev/api>
12. Anthropic REST API description: <https://docs.anthropic.com/en/api>
13. Repository Anthropic Python: <https://github.com/anthropics/anthropic-sdk-python>
14. Webpage vLLM: <https://docs.vllm.ai>
15. Repository LMs4Text2SPARQL Dataset: <https://github.com/AKSW/LMs4Text2SPARQL/tree/main/datasets>
16. Project page CoyPu: <https://coypu.org/>
17. Repository Beastiary dataset and KG: <https://github.com/danrd/sparqlgen>

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